

On the rareness of ‘certain sequences of wavefunctions’ converging to the Gaussian wavefunction

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Abstract: The Kennard inequality in quantum mechanics is the most basic uncertainty relation. Within the framework of the Kennard inequality, the Gaussian wavefunction is the minimum uncertainty wavefunction. Then, is there at least one sequence of real-valued wavefunctions: such that the absolute squares of all wavefunctions that constitute the sequence are a single statistical-distribution which is differentiable everywhere; such that each wavefunction constituting the sequence is a non-Gaussian wavefunction; such that we can calculate the product of the position and momentum uncertainties of each wavefunction in exact closed-form and can make a general description of all those product values; such that another sequence consisting of the product values converges to half the Dirac constant? The answer is yes! This article aims to show (probably all) such sequences. Proofs of convergence to the Gaussian distribution are not only simple but also interesting and instructive.

1. Introduction

Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle is considered as one of the most famous foundations of quantum mechanics. Heisenberg’s article about the uncertainty principle was published in 1927.¹ It was shortly thereafter that Earle Hesse Kennard derived $\sigma_x \sigma_p \geq \hbar/2$ describing the uncertainty principle, where σ_x and σ_p are the standard deviations of position x and linear momentum p .² Since then, we have traditionally been using the Kennard inequality as the most representative uncertainty relation.³⁻⁶ Within the framework of the Kennard inequality, the Gaussian wavefunction is the minimum uncertainty wavefunction. For non-Gaussian wavefunction, the product of the position and momentum uncertainties is greater than half the Dirac constant. One might question whether there is at least one sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of real-valued wavefunctions that meets all of the four requirements: (1) the absolute squares of all wavefunctions that constitute the sequence are a single statistical-distribution which is differentiable everywhere; (2) each wavefunction $\psi_n(x)$ that constitutes the sequence is a non-Gaussian wavefunction; (3) we can make, as a function of n , a general description of all products of the position uncertainty and linear-momentum uncertainty of each individual wavefunction in exact closed-form; (4) another sequence $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ consisting of those product values converges to half the Dirac

constant. I will show the readers (probably all) the sequences which meet all of the four requirements. Meanwhile, every subsequence of a convergent sequence converges to the limit of the original sequence.^{7,8} Throughout this article we will not take into account the subsequences whose original sequence meets all of the requirements. We do not count those subsequences; that is, we will not treat those subsequences as distinct solutions.

We will look at a few specific sequences which meet all of the requirements that have just been said. Because meeting all our requirements is very demanding, delving deeply into such specific sequences is interesting. The reproductive property of certain statistical-distributions and the central limit theorem are the key points in this article. Presumably a majority of physicists are pretty familiar with the central limit theorem. But, only a minority of physicists must be familiar with the reproductive property. Nonetheless, in this article the application of that theorem and that property will catch your eye.

Additionally, we will obtain a somewhat unexpected harvest in the process of solving the problem I raise. The harvest is that we can classify real-valued wavefunctions according to the calculability of uncertainties although classifying the wavefunctions is not what I originally intended.

2. Discussions

For our purposes we have to do a lot of complicated integral calculations. But integration techniques are not our main concern in this article. So, detailed calculation steps will be omitted. Readers can check those calculations in separate Mathematica Notebook files.

Section 2 is organized as follows. In Subsection 2.1 to 2.4, the (probably) complete solutions to our problem are provided. Then, in Subsection 2.5 we will look at a large number of examples which meet some or none of the requirements. In that subsection the readers come to figure out to some extent the stringency of our requirements. Although Subsection 2.5 is optional, that subsection especially is significant in that you will find the contents of this article extraordinarily interesting.

Throughout this article, i denotes the imaginary unit, k denotes the wavenumber, notation $\langle \quad \rangle$ represents the expectation value, $\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty t^{z-1} e^{-t} dt$ is the gamma function, and $H(x)$ is the unit step function which is also called the Heaviside step function.

Meanwhile, all wavefunctions appearing in this article have already been normalized to 1.

2.1. Erlang Distribution

We start this subsection with Theorem 1.

Theorem 1 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{(n+1)! e^x}}$$

where the position is in the range $x \geq 0$. Then, another sequence $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ consisting of the products of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty of those wavefunctions converges to $\hbar/2$.

Proof 1 We calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\langle x \rangle &= \int_0^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x dx = n + 2; \\ \langle x^2 \rangle &= \int_0^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x^2 dx = (n + 3)(n + 2); \\ \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2} &= \sqrt{n + 2}.\end{aligned}$$

Now we do the following calculations on the wavenumber:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_n(k) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(n+1)!}} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ikx}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{e^x}} dx = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{(n+1)!} \sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{(0.5 + ik)^{\frac{n+3}{2}}}; \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 dk &= \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{(n+1)! 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{|(0.5 + ik)^{n+3}|} dk = 1; \\ \langle k \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k dk = 0; \\ \langle k^2 \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k^2 dk = \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{(n+1)! 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{|(0.5 + ik)^{n+3}|} dk = \frac{1}{4n}; \\ \sqrt{\langle k^2 \rangle - \langle k \rangle^2} &= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n}}.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the product of the two uncertainties of each wavefunction is

$$M(n) = \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\frac{n+2}{n}}.$$

Hence, the limiting value is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(n) = \hbar/2$. This $\hbar/2$ is the infimum value of the set $\{M(n) | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ but not the minimum value. \square

The reader should check the correctness of Proof 1 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 1).

The normal distribution is defined on the whole real line. On the other hand, the range of position in Theorem 1 is not the whole real line. So, at first glance, Theorem 1 surprises us. As we will see after a while, the range of position does not matter.

The sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Theorem 1 must not contain $\psi_0(x) = \sqrt{x/e^x}$, because integral of

$$|\phi_0(k)|^2 k^2 = \frac{k^2}{|1 + 2ik|^3}$$

does not converge on $-\infty < k < \infty$.

Although we proved the convergence of the $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, we did not prove that the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2$ is a normal distribution. In Proof 1, calculating the quantum uncertainties required evaluating several difficult integrals. Is it possible that without calculating at all we know that the $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2$ is a normal distribution? The answer is yes, provided that we recognize that each $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is an Erlang distribution! The Erlang distribution is a special case of the gamma distribution, and is a generalization of the exponential distribution. The probability density of the Erlang distribution with shape parameter $s \in \mathbb{N}$ and rate parameter $r > 0$ is given by

$$f(x; s, r) = \frac{r^s}{(s-1)!} \frac{x^{s-1}}{e^{rx}} H(x).^9$$

Let $\text{Erlang}[s, r]$ represent an Erlang distribution with shape parameter s and rate parameter r . The mean and variance of the $\text{Erlang}[s, r]$ are s/r and s/r^2 , respectively. The Erlang distribution has the reproductive property.¹⁰ Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p be independent random variates such that each X_i has an $\text{Erlang}[1, 1]$. The reproductive property of the Erlang distribution states that $\sum_{i=1}^p X_i$ has an $\text{Erlang}[p, 1]$. We can utilize this property for proving the convergence of $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2$. Additionally, we utilize the central limit theorem which is usually abbreviated to CLT. The CLT is valued highly as one of the most important results in probability theory. If V_1, V_2, \dots, V_Q are independent random variates having distributions with means μ_i and finite variances σ_i^2 , then $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^Q V_i$ has a normal distribution with mean $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^Q \mu_i$ and variance $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^Q \sigma_i^2$. The CLT says that the sum of a large number of independent random variates is approximately normally distributed.¹¹ Now, we apply the reproductive property and the CLT to our situation.

Theorem 2 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{(n+1)! e^{x'}}$$

where the position is in the range $x \geq 0$. Then, another sequence $\{|\psi_n(x)|^2\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to the probability density function of a normal distribution.

Proof 2 $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is an $\text{Erlang}[n+2, 1]$. Therefore, by the reproductive property of the Erlang distribution, $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is the probability density of $\sum_{i=1}^{n+2} X_i$. Therefore, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2$ converges to the probability density function of a normal distribution by the CLT. \square

We see that the convergence was proved with much less effort in this way than by using a direct calculation.

2.2. Chi-Square Distribution

The chi-square distribution is a special case of the gamma distribution. The probability density of the chi-square distribution with ν degrees of freedom is given by

$$f(x; \nu) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^\nu} \Gamma\left(\frac{\nu}{2}\right)} \frac{x^{\frac{\nu}{2}-1}}{\exp\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)} H(x),$$

where ν is any positive value.¹² Let $\text{chisquare}[\nu]$ represent a chi-square distribution with ν degrees of freedom.

Theorem 3 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{(n+1)! 2^{n+2} \exp\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)}}$$

where the position is in the range $x \geq 0$. Then, another sequence $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ consisting of the products of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty of those wavefunctions converges to $\hbar/2$.

Proof 3 We calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\langle x \rangle &= \int_0^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x dx = 2(n+2); \\ \langle x^2 \rangle &= \int_0^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x^2 dx = 4(n+3)(n+2); \\ \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2} &= 2\sqrt{n+2}.\end{aligned}$$

Now we do the following calculations on the wavenumber:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_n(k) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(n+1)! 2^{n+2}}} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ikx}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{\exp \frac{x}{2}}} dx = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{(n+1)!} \sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{(0.5 + 2ik)^{\frac{n+3}{2}}}; \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 dk &= \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{(n+1)! \pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{|(0.5 + 2ik)^{n+3}|} dk = 1; \\ \langle k \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k dk = 0; \\ \langle k^2 \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k^2 dk = \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{(n+1)! \pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{|(0.5 + 2ik)^{n+3}|} dk = \frac{1}{16n}; \\ \sqrt{\langle k^2 \rangle - \langle k \rangle^2} &= \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n}}.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the product of the two uncertainties of each wavefunction is

$$M(n) = \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\frac{n+2}{n}}.$$

Hence, the limiting value is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(n) = \hbar/2$. This $\hbar/2$ is the infimum value of the set $\{M(n) | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ but not the minimum value. \square

The reader should check the correctness of Proof 3 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 2).

The sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Theorem 3 must not contain $\psi_0(x) = e^{-x/2}x/4$, because $\langle k^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds. And, this sequence must not contain $\psi_{-1}(x) = e^{-x/2}/2$, because integral of

$$|\phi_{-1}(k)|^2 k = \frac{4k}{|\mathbb{i} - 4k|^2 \pi}$$

does not converge on $-\infty < k < \infty$ and $\langle k^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds.

The chi-square distribution as well as the Erlang distribution has the reproductive property.¹⁰ Meanwhile, the chi-square distribution converges to a normal distribution as the number of degrees of freedom tends to infinity.¹³ We can easily prove the convergence of sequence $\{|\psi_n(x)|^2\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ using the CLT this time, too.

Theorem 4 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{x^{n+1}}{(n+1)! 2^{n+2} \exp \frac{x}{2}}}$$

where the position is in the range $x \geq 0$. Then, another sequence $\{|\psi_n(x)|^2\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to the probability density function of a normal distribution.

Proof 4 $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is a chisquare $[2n + 4]$. Let Y_1, Y_2, \dots be independent random variates such that each Y_i has a chisquare $[1]$. By the reproductive property of the chi-square distribution, $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is the probability density of $\sum_{i=1}^{2n+4} Y_i$. Therefore, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2$ converges to the probability density function of a normal distribution by the CLT. \square

2.3. Student's t Distribution

Let C be a positive constant. Because the statistical distributions of Theorem 1 and the statistical distributions of Theorem 2 are special cases of statistical distribution $C^{n+2}x^{n+1}/(n+1)!e^{Cx}$, let us consider such sequences a single solution to our problem. Subsections 2.1 and 2.2 are not saying that there is only one solution. In the previous two subsections we discussed the two statistical distributions having the reproductive property. But a mystery remains: how many sequences meet all our requirements? Can we create a sequence such that the squared moduli of wavefunctions constituting the sequence are the distribution which does not have the reproductive property. There is such a sequence.

Theorem 5 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{(n+2)\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{x^2}{n+2}\right)^{n+3}}}$$

where the position is in the range $-\infty < x < +\infty$. Then, another sequence $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ consisting of the products of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty of those wavefunctions converges to $\hbar/2$.

Proof 5 We calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x dx = 0; \\ \langle x^2 \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x^2 dx = \frac{n+2}{n}; \\ \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2} &= \sqrt{\frac{n+2}{n}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we do the following calculations on the wavenumber:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_n(k) &= \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{(n+2)\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ikx}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{x^2}{n+2}\right)^{n+3}}} dx \\ &= \frac{(n+2)^{\frac{n+3}{8}} |k|^{\frac{n+1}{4}} K_{\frac{n+1}{4}}(\sqrt{n+2}|k|)}{\sqrt{\sqrt{2^{n-1}\pi}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{4}\right)} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $K_{\frac{n+1}{4}}(z)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind¹⁴;

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 dk = 1;$$

$$\langle k \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k dk = 0;$$

$$\langle k^2 \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k^2 dk = \frac{n+3}{4(n+5)};$$

$$\sqrt{\langle k^2 \rangle - \langle k \rangle^2} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{n+3}{n+5}}.$$

Therefore, the product of the two uncertainties of each wavefunction is

$$M(n) = \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(n+3)(n+2)}{(n+5)n}}.$$

Hence, the limiting value is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(n) = \hbar/2$. This $\hbar/2$ is the infimum value of the set $\{M(n) | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ but not the minimum value. □

The reader should check the correctness of Proof 5 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 3). The sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Theorem 5 must not contain

$$\psi_0(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma(1.5)}{\Gamma(1) \sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{x^2}{2}\right)^{1.5}}},$$

because the variance of x is indeterminate. And this sequence must not contain

$$\psi_{-1}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(0.5) \sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{1+x^2}},$$

because the variance and mean of x are indeterminate.

In fact, each $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is a Student's t distribution¹⁵. The Student's t distribution converges to a normal distribution as n tends to infinity.¹⁶

2.4. Chi Distribution

This sequence is probably the last sequence that meets all our requirements.

Theorem 6 Let n be any positive integer. Consider a sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of the normalized wavefunctions

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)} \frac{x^{n+1}}{\exp\left(\frac{x^2}{2}\right)}}$$

where the position is in the range $x \geq 0$. Then, another sequence $\{M(n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ consisting of the products of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty of those wavefunctions converges to $\hbar/2$.

Proof 6 We calculate the following:

$$\langle x \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x dx = \frac{\sqrt{2} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)};$$

$$\langle x^2 \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 x^2 dx = n + 2;$$

$$\sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2} = \sqrt{n + 2 - \frac{2 \Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)}}.$$

Now we do the following calculations on the wavenumber:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_n(k) &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ikx}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)} \frac{x^{n+1}}{\exp\frac{x^2}{2}}} dx \\ &= \frac{\sqrt[4]{2^n} \left\{ \Gamma\left(\frac{n+3}{4}\right) {}_1F_1\left(\frac{n+3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}; -k^2\right) - 2ik \Gamma\left(\frac{n+5}{4}\right) {}_1F_1\left(\frac{n+5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}; -k^2\right) \right\}}{\sqrt{\pi \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)}} \end{aligned}$$

where ${}_1F_1(\ ; \ ; \)$ represents the Kummer confluent hypergeometric function¹⁷;

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 dk = 1;$$

$$\langle k \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k dk = 0;$$

$$\langle k^2 \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(k)|^2 k^2 dk = \frac{2n+1}{4n};$$

$$\sqrt{\langle k^2 \rangle - \langle k \rangle^2} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{2n+1}{n}}.$$

Therefore, the product of the two uncertainties of each wavefunction is

$$M(n) = \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{n + 2 - \frac{2 \Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+3}{2}\right)}{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)}} \sqrt{2 + \frac{1}{n}}.$$

Hence, the limiting value is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(n) = \hbar/2$. This $\hbar/2$ is the infimum value of the set $\{M(n) | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ but not the minimum value. □

The reader should check the correctness of Proof 6 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 4).

The sequence $\{\psi_n(x)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Theorem 6 must not contain

$$\psi_0(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Gamma(1)} \frac{x}{\exp\frac{x^2}{2}}}$$

because $\langle k^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds. And this sequence must not contain

$$\psi_{-1}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \frac{1}{\exp\frac{x^2}{2}}}$$

because $\langle k \rangle$ does not converge on $-\infty < k < \infty$ and $\langle k^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds.

In fact, each $|\psi_n(x)|^2$ is a chi distribution. The chi distribution is not a special case of the gamma distribution. The probability density of the chi distribution with ν degrees of freedom is given by

$$f(x; \nu) = \frac{2^{1-\frac{\nu}{2}} x^{\nu-1}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu}{2}\right) \exp\frac{x^2}{2}} H(x),$$

where ν is any positive real number.¹⁸ The chi distribution converges to a normal distribution as $\nu \rightarrow \infty$.

2.5. Supplementary Examples

In the preceding subsections we have been concerned with solutions to our problem. It is important that the readers understand the fact that meeting all our requirements is stringent. Let us understand such a fact through various examples. In current subsection we will see various sequences which are not solutions.

There are various types of the sequences which meet requirements (1) and (2) which were mentioned in Section 1. Such sequences may be categorized into 5 types according to the calculability of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty. We will investigate those types. Let us check some examples for each type. A first type is one such that we can make a general description of the product of the two uncertainties of each individual wavefunction and such that the product infinitely increases as n tends to infinity. As two representative cases, let us consider the n th stationary states of the infinite square well with width a and of the quantum harmonic oscillator. In each case the product of the two uncertainties infinitely increases as n tends to infinity.¹⁹ These two cases are listed in Table 1. In this table, $H_{n-1}(\eta)$ is a Hermite polynomial of degree $n - 1$ in η , where $\eta \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{m\omega/\hbar} x$.

Table 1 A first type of the evaluation result of the two uncertainties

Wavefunction	$\langle x \rangle$	$\langle x^2 \rangle$	$\langle k \rangle$	$\langle k^2 \rangle$	$\sigma_x \times \sigma_k$
$\sqrt{\frac{2}{a}} \sin \frac{n\pi x}{a} \quad \because 0 \leq x \leq a$	$\frac{a}{2}$	$\left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{2n^2\pi^2}\right) a^2$	0	$\left(\frac{n\pi}{a}\right)^2$	$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(n\pi)^2}{3} - 2}$
$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n! 2^n}} \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar}} \frac{H_{n-1}(\eta)}{\exp\frac{m\omega x^2}{2\hbar}}$	0	$\frac{(n-0.5)\hbar}{m\omega}$	0	$\frac{(n-0.5)m\omega}{\hbar}$	$\sqrt{\frac{(n-0.5)\hbar}{m\omega}} \sqrt{\frac{(n-0.5)m\omega}{\hbar}} = n - 0.5$

A second type is one such that $\langle x \rangle$ and $\langle x^2 \rangle$ are well calculated in exact closed-form but such that $\langle k \rangle$ or $\langle k^2 \rangle$ does not converge or is not calculated in exact closed-form. For example, let us consider a sequence $\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{3(n^2 - x^2)}{4n^3}} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of wavefunctions, where the position is in the range $-n \leq x \leq n$. For this sequence, $\langle x \rangle = 0$ and $\langle x^2 \rangle = n^2/5$ and $\langle k \rangle = 0$ hold. Unfortunately, however, $\langle k^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds. Thus, the product of the two uncertainties of each individual wavefunction is not expressed as a function of n . Several examples of this type are listed in Table 2. In this table, $\zeta(\)$ is the Riemann zeta function and \mathcal{E} is the Euler constant.

Table 2 A second type of the evaluation result of the two uncertainties

Wavefunction	$\langle x \rangle$	$\langle x^2 \rangle$	$\langle k \rangle$	$\langle k^2 \rangle$	$\sigma_x \times \sigma_k$
$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2n}} \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{n^2}{3}$	0	∞	
$\sqrt{\frac{3(n^2 - x^2)}{4n^3}} \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{n^2}{5}$	0	∞	
$\sqrt{\frac{5(n^4 - x^4)}{8n^5}} \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{5n^2}{21}$	0	indeterminate	
$\sqrt{\frac{n \exp[-(nx)^4]}{2 \Gamma(\frac{5}{4})}}$	0	$\frac{\Gamma(\frac{3}{4})}{n^2 \Gamma(\frac{1}{4})}$	0	indeterminate	
$\sqrt{\frac{(n+1)x^n}{\exp x^{n+1}}} \quad \because x \geq 0$	$\Gamma(\frac{n+2}{n+1})$	$\Gamma(\frac{n+3}{n+1})$	indeterminate	indeterminate	
$\frac{\sqrt{\Gamma(4n+2)}}{\Gamma(2n+1)} \frac{x^n}{(1+x)^{2n+1}} \quad \because x \geq 0$	$\frac{2n+1}{2n}$	$\frac{(2n+1)(n+1)}{(2n-1)n}$	indeterminate	indeterminate	
$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\zeta(2n+1) \Gamma(2n+1)}} \frac{x^n}{\sqrt{e^x - 1}} \quad \because x \geq 0$	$\frac{(2n+1) \zeta(2n+2)}{\zeta(2n+1)}$	$\frac{2(n+1)(2n+1) \zeta(2n+3)}{\zeta(2n+1)}$	indeterminate	indeterminate	
$\frac{n}{\sqrt{1+n}} \sqrt{\frac{x+1}{e^{nx}}} \quad \because x \geq 0$	$\frac{n+2}{(n+1)n}$	$\frac{2(n+3)}{(n+1)n^2}$	∞	∞	
$\sqrt{\frac{n}{\exp[nx + \exp[-nx]]}}$	$\frac{\varepsilon}{n}$	$\frac{6\varepsilon^2 + \pi^2}{6n^2}$	indeterminate	indeterminate	

The reader should check the correctness of Table 2 using Mathematica Notebook files (Online Resources 5 through 13).

A third type is one such that $\langle k \rangle$ and $\langle k^2 \rangle$ are well calculated in exact closed-form but such that $\langle x \rangle$ or $\langle x^2 \rangle$ does not converge or is not calculated in exact closed-form. An example of this type is listed in Table 3. Let us consider a sequence $\left\{ \sqrt{\frac{n}{(x^2 + n^2)\pi}} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of wavefunctions, where the position is in the range $-\infty < x < \infty$. For this sequence, $\langle x \rangle = 0$ holds, but $\langle x^2 \rangle = \infty$ holds. Thus, the product of the two uncertainties of each individual wavefunction is not expressed as a function of n .

Table 3 A third type of the evaluation result of the two uncertainties

Wavefunction	$\langle x \rangle$	$\langle x^2 \rangle$	$\langle k \rangle$	$\langle k^2 \rangle$	$\sigma_x \times \sigma_k$
$\sqrt{\frac{n}{(x^2 + n^2)\pi}}$	0	∞	0	$\frac{1}{8n^2}$	

The reader should check the correctness of Table 3 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 14).

A fourth type is one such that $\langle x \rangle$ or $\langle x^2 \rangle$ does not converge or is not calculated in exact closed-form and such that $\langle k \rangle$ or $\langle k^2 \rangle$ does not converge or is not calculated in exact closed-form. An example of this type is listed in Table 4. This example is about the Lévy distribution²⁰.

Table 4 A fourth type of the evaluation result of the two uncertainties

Wavefunction	$\langle x \rangle$	$\langle x^2 \rangle$	$\langle k \rangle$	$\langle k^2 \rangle$	$\sigma_x \times \sigma_k$
$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n\pi}} \frac{1}{x^{1.5} \exp \frac{1}{nx}} \quad \because x > 0$	∞	∞	indeterminate	indeterminate	

The reader should check the correctness of Table 4 using Mathematica Notebook file (Online Resource 15).

A fifth type as a last type is one such that the products of the two uncertainties are the same number. So sequences of this type do not meet requirement (4). These sequences are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 A fifth type of the evaluation result of the two uncertainties

Wavefunction	$\langle x \rangle$	$\langle x^2 \rangle$	$\langle k \rangle$	$\langle k^2 \rangle$	$\sigma_x \times \sigma_k$
$\sqrt{\frac{15n}{16}} \operatorname{sech}^3 nx$	0	$\frac{2\pi^2 - 15}{24n^2}$	0	$\frac{9n^2}{7}$	$\sqrt{\frac{2\pi^2 - 15}{24n^2}} \sqrt{\frac{9n^2}{7}} = \sqrt{\frac{3(2\pi^2 - 15)}{56}} \approx 0.504$
$\sqrt{\frac{3n}{4}} \operatorname{sech}^2 nx$	0	$\frac{\pi^2 - 6}{12n^2}$	0	$\frac{4n^2}{5}$	$\sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 - 6}{12n^2}} \sqrt{\frac{4n^2}{5}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 - 6}{15}} \approx 0.508$
$\sqrt{\frac{3003}{2048n^{13}}} (n^2 - x^2)^3 \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{n^2}{15}$	0	$\frac{39}{10n^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{n^2}{15}} \sqrt{\frac{39}{10n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{13}{50}} \approx 0.510$
$\sqrt{\frac{315}{256n^9}} (n^2 - x^2)^2 \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{n^2}{11}$	0	$\frac{3}{n^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{n^2}{11}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{11}} \approx 0.522$
$\sqrt{\frac{n}{2}} \operatorname{sech} nx$	0	$\frac{\pi^2}{12n^2}$	0	$\frac{n^2}{3}$	$\sqrt{\frac{\pi^2}{12n^2}} \sqrt{\frac{n^2}{3}} = \frac{\pi}{6} \approx 0.524$
$\sqrt{\frac{4\sqrt{2}n}{3\pi}} \frac{n^3}{x^4 + n^4}$	0	$\frac{n^2}{3}$	0	$\frac{5}{6n^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{n^2}{3}} \sqrt{\frac{5}{6n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{5}{18}} \approx 0.527$
$\sqrt{\frac{9n}{5\pi}} \frac{n^5}{x^6 + n^6}$	0	$\frac{3n^2}{10}$	0	$\frac{7}{6n^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{3n^2}{10}} \sqrt{\frac{7}{6n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{7}{20}} \approx 0.592$
$\sqrt{\frac{15}{16n^5}} (n^2 - x^2) \quad \because x \leq n$	0	$\frac{n^2}{7}$	0	$\frac{5}{2n^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{n^2}{7}} \sqrt{\frac{5}{2n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{5}{14}} \approx 0.598$
$\sqrt{\frac{2n}{\pi}} \frac{n}{x^2 + n^2}$	0	n^2	0	$\frac{1}{2n^2}$	$\sqrt{n^2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 0.707$

The reader should check the correctness of Table 5 using Mathematica Notebook files (Online Resources 16 through 24).

After seeing Table 5, the reader might create a sequence $\left\{ (1 - x^2)^n \sqrt{\Gamma(2n + 1.5) / \sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(2n + 1)} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of wavefunctions, in which case the product of the two uncertainties is a function of n . And then the reader might try to obtain the limit value of the sequence of the products of the two uncertainties. We can obtain $\langle x \rangle = 0$ and $\langle x^2 \rangle = 1/(4n + 3)$ and $\langle k \rangle = 0$. But it is impossible to calculate $\langle k^2 \rangle$ in the form which we desire: we cannot make a general description of $\langle k^2 \rangle$ as a function of n in closed form. Please note here that although for each specific n we can obtain all four expectation values, we cannot make a general description of $\langle k^2 \rangle$ which holds for all n 's. Likewise, after seeing Table 5, the reader might create other sequences and try to obtain their respective limit values. But, you will fail to complete all calculations.

The content of this subsection is important in order that we figure out to some extent the stringency of our requirements.

3. Conclusions

Statistical distributions are either discrete or continuous, depending on whether they define probabilities for discrete or continuous variates. Probably, we have fully solved the proposed problem. I tested not only the continuous distributions mentioned in this article but also many continuous distributions not mentioned in this article. For most distributions, it was too difficult or even impossible to obtain explicit expression for the product of the position uncertainty and the momentum uncertainty. The complete solutions to my problem depend on how many integration techniques have been developed.

The fact that sequences of the Erlang distributions and of the chi-square distributions converge to a normal distribution may be puzzling at first sight. The reason is that the Erlang distribution and the chi-square distribution are zero on the non-positive real line. However, the support of a statistical distribution does not matter in the central limit theorem. We utilized the reproductive property of these two distributions, thereby being able to easily prove the convergence.

Just because a sequence of wavefunctions converges to a normal distribution does not mean the sequence meets all our requirements that have been mentioned in the introduction. Even if it is easy to prove that a sequence of wavefunctions converges to a normal distribution and that a sequence of the products of the two quantum uncertainties converges to half the Dirac constant, it is very difficult in most instances to make a general description of those products in the form which we desire. It is almost certain that there are no other solutions that meet all the requirements, except the solutions which were already described in this article. If any doubt remains in your mind about my argument, try to create your own sequence that fulfills all the requirements. Whatever sequence the reader creates, "without exception" or "with very few exceptions" you will not be able to complete the calculations in exact closed-form. And hence you will not be able to make a general description of the calculation results. Meeting all of our requirements is very demanding.

Lastly, I would like to say that Theorems 1 through 4 are the content worth being included in the textbooks on quantum mechanics.

Data Availability Statement: The original data presented in the study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19334292>.

References

- [1] Werner K. Heisenberg, “Über den anschaulichen inhalt der quantentheoretischen kinematik und mechanik,” *Z. Physik* 43 (3-4), 172–198 (1927).
- [2] Earle H. Kennard, “Zur quantenmechanik einfacher bewegungstypen,” *Z. Physik* 44 (4-5), 326–352 (1927).
- [3] Eugen Merzbacher, *Quantum Mechanics*, 3rd Ed. (John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, 1998), pp. 14–18.
- [4] Richard L. Liboff, *Introductory Quantum Mechanics*, 4th Ed. (Addison Wesley, San Francisco, CA, 2003), pp. 53–54.
- [5] David J. Griffiths and Darrell F. Schroeter, *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics*, 3rd Ed. (Cambridge University Press, UK, 2018), pp. 19–20.
- [6] Philip L. Bowers, *Lectures on Quantum Mechanics : A Primer for Mathematicians* (Cambridge University Press, New York, NY, 2020), pp. 125–127.
- [7] William R. Wade, *An Introduction to Analysis*, 4th Ed. Global Ed. (Pearson Education, Harlow, UK, 2022), pp. 55–60.
- [8] Steven G. Krantz, *Real Analysis and Foundations*, 5th Ed. (CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2022), pp. 90–95.
- [9] Catherine Forbes, Merran Evans, Nicholas Hastings, and Brian Peacock, *Statistical Distributions*, 4th Ed. (Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, 2011), pp. 84–85.
- [10] Robert Hogg, Joseph McKean, and Allen Craig, *Introduction to Mathematical Statistics*, 8th Ed. (Pearson, Boston, MA, 2019), p. 177.
- [11] Hans Fischer, *A History of the Central Limit Theorem* (Springer New York, NY, 2011), p. 3.
- [12] Catherine Forbes, Merran Evans, Nicholas Hastings, and Brian Peacock, *Statistical Distributions*, 4th Ed. (Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, 2011), pp. 69–70.
- [13] Brian R. Martin, *Statistics for Physical Sciences* (Academic Press, Waltham, MA, 2012), p. 109.
- [14] Wolfram Research (1988), BesselK, Wolfram Language function, <https://reference.wolfram.com/language/ref/BesselK.html> (updated 2022). (Accessed: 2 July 2026).
- [15] Catherine Forbes, Merran Evans, Nicholas Hastings, and Brian Peacock, *Statistical Distributions*, 4th Ed. (Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, 2011), pp. 183–185.
- [16] Brian R. Martin, *Statistics for Physical Sciences* (Academic Press, Waltham, MA, 2012), p. 113.
- [17] Wolfram Research (1988), Hypergeometric1F1, Wolfram Language function, <https://reference.wolfram.com/language/ref/Hypergeometric1F1.html> (updated 2022). (Accessed: 2 July 2026).
- [18] Catherine Forbes, Merran Evans, Nicholas Hastings, and Brian Peacock, *Statistical Distributions*, 4th Ed. (Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, 2011), p. 73.
- [19] David J. Griffiths and Darrell F. Schroeter, *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics*, 3rd Ed. (Cambridge University Press, UK, 2018), pp. 37,48.
- [20] Wolfram Research (2008), LevyDistribution, Wolfram Language function, <https://reference.wolfram.com/language/ref/LevyDistribution.html> (updated 2016). (Accessed: 2 July 2026).